

NDAC/LO/023

1983 July 7

Fifth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

1. Process Definitions

Definitions of the PRS Solution (NDAC/LO/021) and Back-Substitution (022) have been distributed since the previous report (019). Two important modifications have been made with respect to the original ideas:

- (i) Instead of eliminating the set zero points from the PRS normals, we now propose to eliminate the astrometric parameters and solving for the zero points and global distortion parameters. This will reduce the size of the system and computation time significantly. The subset of Primary Reference Stars can also be enlarged to include practically all 'single' stars, or perhaps 60 % of the programme stars (020-021).
- (ii) The Back-Substitution is now regarded as a simple subprocess of the PRS Solution, in that the elimination of slit errors (mesh method) and preadjustment of the astrometric parameters is done simultaneously with the accumulation of PRS normals (022).

Our concepts about the data reductions have evolved quite significantly since the first Process Definition 14 months ago, with the result that the earlier definitions are sometimes incomplete or inconsistent with later ones. After the final definition (WP8100: Double Stars, expected in September), it will be necessary to review the entire reduction scheme and perhaps put together a definition synthesis. In order to make time for this, we propose to delay the start of WP8200 till the beginning of 1984.

2. Work in progress

A report by Söderhjelm on the small scale (20 stars) PRS experiments will appear by mid-July.

Algorithms and datamatic aspects of using a spline representation of the attitude in the Set Solution are being studied ('Numerical Smoothing'). No fundamental difficulty has been identified, but computing time may increase drastically (compared with the 'geometrical' solution) as a result of the much denser normal equations.

3. WP6200: PRS Solution (Algorithm Development)

Through a grant from the SBSA, Söderhjelm is working 75 % on the project during a year starting on July 1. By agreement with the Danish Colleagues, he will perform simulations and develop specific routines for the PRS solution. These tasks are detailed in 'Contributions from Lund to WP6200-6300'.

4. Meetings

Participants from CUO, DSRI, GI, and LO met twice in Copenhagen and once in Lund during the period. On May 9-12, Lindegren visited RGO (Murray, van Leeuwen), MSSL (Cruise, Allison-Smith), and UCL (McNally, Fawell). The main topics were the attitude reconstitution, OTF calibration, simulation of IDT data, relativity, and TYCHO analysis.

5. References

- NDAC/LO/020 A possible variant of the PRS solution (2pp)
NDAC/LO/021 WP6100: PRS Solution (Definition) (20pp)
NDAC/LO/022 WP7100: Back-Substitution (Definition) (12pp)
NDAC/LO/023 Fifth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory (2pp)
- 1983 May 26 Proposal for an improved Great Circle Reduction formula (30pp)
1983 Jun 15 Contributions ffrom Lund to WP6200-6300 (2pp)